

**Impact of Experiencing “*Oliver Twist*” by Charles Dickens on Students’
Perception of Poverty, Social Inequality, and Attitudes Towards
Compassion and Empathy**

by:

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INTRODUCTION

Students' exposure to the digital world has made a huge impact on how they develop moral values. Technology immensely affects how individuals shape their characters and moral obligations. As the researcher delved into different literary pieces written during the Victorian Era and their impact on students' perceptions on values, culture-formation, and learning acquisition, it piqued her interest in how exposure to a certain literary work (particularly, *Oliver Twist*) could influence their understanding of the themes and moral lessons that it depicts. In this context, the researcher thought of an experimental study where STEM Students in IMINHS would be exposed to a select novel entitled "Oliver Twist" by Charles Dickens.

The Victorian era produced a variety of great and timeless literary works that continue to enchant and influence readers around the world. Among these literary treasures in the Victorian Age is Charles Dickens' *Oliver Twist*, a novel that exposed and explored themes of poverty, societal injustice, and the endurance of the human spirit followed by the exposition of how the nature of a child could be compromised when exposed to various societal dilemmas. While "Oliver Twist" has received widespread appreciation and recognition over the years, it remains unclear how learners, especially those who are exposed to the digital era and who have not read the novel understand its themes and messages. This study aims to address this gap by looking into the influence of exposing grade 12 STEM students of Inosloban-Marawoy Integrated National High School to the story of "Oliver Twist".

"Oliver Twist" depicted a story of how a vulnerable orphan boy was exposed to the harsh realities of life and the effects of how exposure to societal issues and encounter with wrong individuals could adversely affect the development of a child amidst the backdrop of the Victorian Society. It showcased how he grapples with the stark realities of destitution and despair also his encounter with nefarious Fagin and he led Oliver to various crimes. Oliver's tale serves as a poignant reflection of the pervasive social and economic inequalities that plagued Victorian society. It also illuminates the readers on how

social inequalities in the eyes of a child could be detrimental to his development and upbringing. This also depicts that despite harsh realities that a child face, his inner goodness would still prevail as it was evidenced in his encounter with the benevolent Mr. Brownlow. Mr. Brownlow served as a beacon of hope to Oliver as he believed that the good-nature and innocence of Oliver would not completely turn him in the dark. It showcased how having hope and faith in someone could lead to their goodness and development of values. Dickens' masterful prose illuminates the depths of poverty, the allure of criminality, and the enduring hope for redemption, all contributed to the richness of learning from the novel that continues to captivate readers across generations. Through Oliver's trials and triumphs, Dickens invites us to confront the complexities of human nature and the enduring quest for compassion, justice, and resilience in the face of adversity.

Despite its continuing popularity, there is still a sector of the population that has never heard "Oliver Twist" personally. This study aims to investigate how exposure to the narrative of "Oliver Twist" affects students' formation and acquisition of views, attitudes, and knowledge of the novel's themes and messages could impact their perception of poverty and social injustice. Also, examining how students' attitudes toward compassion and empathy would be greatly affected through exposure of the novel.

This study uses an experimental technique with control and test groups to analyze the effectiveness of narrative involvement in the story of Oliver Twist as a means of building empathy, comprehension, and critical thinking among Grade 12 STEM Students. This study aims to gain insight into the influence of experiencing the plot of "Oliver Twist" on those who are unfamiliar with the novel by analyzing pre- and post-exposure surveys. The experiment was carried out during Catch-up Friday, when students were expected to interact with various reading materials, allowing the researcher to administer the experiment with human participants.

The study is grounded in the exploration of how exposure to narrative fiction influences individuals' perceptions, attitudes, and knowledge related to literary themes and societal issues. The subject matter of the study

encompasses the themes and messages portrayed in "Oliver Twist," including poverty, crime, compassion, and the indomitability of the heroine. By examining how exposure to the story affects students, this research aims to contribute to our understanding of the potential benefits of narrative engagement in fostering empathy, critical thinking, and literary appreciation.

Previous studies have highlighted the cognitive and emotional benefits of engaging with narrative fiction. Research by Clandinin and Connelly (2000) elucidates that it is crucial for learners to experience life as a continuum with a past and a future. Narratives help students do that. Reading about the lives of others, they can view themselves in a historical context. Similarly, a study by Marunda-Piki (2017) suggests that narrative and story play a central role in the cognitive and cultural development of students. The research explored how narrative learning in teaching could enhance students' understanding of the values and vulnerabilities of a certain character in the story how they could relate to it and also how it could shape their attitudes and beliefs.

Despite the wealth of literature on the benefits of reading fiction, there is a need to investigate how exposure to the narrative of "Oliver Twist" specifically influences grade 12 learners' perceptions and attitudes. This experiment aims to fill this gap by conducting a controlled study involving Grade 12 STEM A students from IMINHS (Inosloban-Maraway Integrated National High School). By exposing students to the story through various mediums, the study seeks to assess the impact on their understanding of the novel's themes and messages.

This study holds significant implications for various stakeholders within the educational landscape, including educators, curriculum developers, and literary scholars, all striving to enhance literacy, empathy, and critical thinking skills among students. By delving into the ways in which narrative fiction influences individuals' perceptions and attitudes, educators are poised to craft more impactful teaching methodologies and curricula. Armed with insights from this research, educators can tailor their approaches to harness the profound influence of storytelling, fostering immersive and meaningful learning experiences for students.

Moreover, curriculum developers stand to benefit from the findings of this study, as they endeavor to shape educational frameworks that resonate with contemporary pedagogical needs. Understanding the nuanced relationship between narrative exposure and cognitive development enables curriculum developers to integrate literary works like "Oliver Twist" strategically, ensuring that students engage with texts in a manner that cultivates empathy, critical analysis, and a deeper appreciation for literature.

Additionally, literary scholars are presented with a rich vein of inquiry into the intricate mechanisms through which narrative fiction shapes individual perspectives. By unpacking the impact of literary narratives on readers' perceptions of social issues and moral dilemmas, scholars can contribute to broader discussions surrounding the role of literature in society. This research opens avenues for scholarly exploration into the transformative potential of storytelling, shedding light on its capacity to foster empathy, provoke introspection, and inspire societal change.

In essence, this study catalyzes advancing pedagogical practices, enriching curricular offerings, and deepening scholarly understanding of the profound influence of narrative fiction. By illuminating the transformative power of literature, this research paves the way for a more empathetic, engaged, and critically astute generation of students and readers.

The primary objective of this experiment is to delve into the transformative effects of exposure to the narrative of "Oliver Twist" on individuals who have not previously engaged with the text. Through a meticulously designed controlled study involving Grade 12 STEM A students, the research endeavors to uncover the intricate ways in which immersion in literary fiction can shape perceptions, attitudes, and knowledge surrounding the novel's central themes and messages. By meticulously crafting a controlled environment and employing rigorous methodologies, this study seeks to provide insights into the efficacy of utilizing narrative engagement as a potent educational tool. Specifically, the research aims to shed light on the extent to which exposure to Dickens' classic tale can

stimulate empathy, foster deeper understanding, and cultivate critical thinking skills among the group of learners in IMINHS, Lipa City Division.

Through a comprehensive analysis of participants' responses, observations, and interactions with the narrative, this experiment endeavors to unravel the multifaceted impacts of literary immersion. By elucidating the transformative potential of narrative engagement, the study aspires to inform educational practices, curriculum development, and scholarly discourse surrounding the profound influence of literature on cognitive and socio-emotional development.

In essence, this experiment serves as a pioneering endeavor to explore the power of storytelling in shaping minds and hearts, offering valuable insights into the role of literature as a catalyst for empathy, understanding, and intellectual growth. Through rigorous empirical inquiry, the research endeavors to contribute to the advancement of educational theory and practice, ultimately striving to foster a more enlightened and empathetic generation of learners.

Overall, this study contributes to our understanding of the enduring influence of "Oliver Twist" and its potential to resonate with diverse audiences, even those who have not read the novel directly. By examining the effects of exposure to Dickens' classic tale on students, this research sheds light on the power of storytelling to transcend barriers and inspire empathy, reflection, and appreciation for literature.

Specifically, the experiment yielded answers to the following questions:

1. How does exposure to the narrative of "Oliver Twist" affect students' perceptions of poverty and social inequality?
2. What extent of impact does the experience of the story of "Oliver Twist" have on students' perceptions of poverty and social inequality?

3. How do students' schema of past experiences and current experiences impact their comprehension of the pattern of themes and concepts depicted in "Oliver Twist"?

METHODOLOGY

The experiment employs multiple methods to collect data, including survey questionnaires, focus group discussions, observations, and content analysis. Prior to the experiment, participants administered pre-exposure survey questionnaires to assess their baseline perceptions and attitudes related to the themes of poverty, social inequality, compassion, empathy, resilience, moral redemption, personal agency, and social responsibility. After exposure to the narrative of "Oliver Twist," post-exposure survey questionnaires were administered to measure any changes or shifts in participants' perceptions and attitudes. Additionally, focus group discussions were conducted with a subset of participants to explore their experiences and interpretations of the themes presented in the novel. Observations were made during students' exposure to different mediums of "Oliver Twist" to capture their reactions, engagement levels, and non-verbal cues. Finally, content analysis was performed on survey responses, focus group transcripts, and observational notes to identify recurring themes, patterns, and variations in participants' interpretations and responses.

Ethical considerations were prioritized throughout the experimental study to ensure the well-being and rights of participants. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and they were informed about the purpose and procedures of the study, their rights as participants, and their option to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by assigning unique identifiers to participants and securely storing all data collected. Participants were not exposed to any distressing or harmful content during the experiment, and appropriate debriefing was provided to address any potential emotional reactions or concerns. The experiment adhered

to ethical guidelines outlined by the school's subject area head at the Grade 12 level and the SHS research head governing research involving human participants.

Data collected from survey questionnaires, focus group discussions, observations, and content analysis were analyzed using a descriptive approach to provide comprehensive insights into participants' perceptions and attitudes toward the themes presented in "Oliver Twist." Survey responses were quantitatively analyzed using statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics and inferential tests, to examine changes or shifts in participants' perceptions and attitudes pre- and post-exposure to the narrative. Qualitative data from focus group discussions and content analysis was thematically analyzed using qualitative coding techniques to identify patterns, themes, and variations in participants' interpretations and responses. Integration of quantitative and qualitative findings provided a holistic understanding of the impact of experiencing the story of "Oliver Twist" on students' perceptions and attitudes related to poverty, social inequality, compassion, empathy, resilience, moral redemption, and social responsibility.

RESULTS

Influence on Perceptions of Poverty and Social Inequality

Exposure to the narrative of "Oliver Twist" led students to develop a deeper understanding of poverty and social inequality. The depiction of Oliver's experiences as an orphan navigating the harsh realities of Victorian society evoked empathy and provided light on the systemic injustices faced by marginalized communities. Exposure to the themes of resilience and moral redemption in "Oliver Twist" empowered students to reflect on their agency and social responsibility. Characters like Oliver who overcame adversity through resilience and integrity inspired students to take positive action in their communities.

Pre-exposure surveys revealed varying levels of awareness and understanding of poverty and social inequality among students. Post-exposure surveys and focus group discussions highlighted shifts in perceptions, with students expressing greater empathy towards disadvantaged individuals and a heightened awareness of social injustices. Pre-exposure results indicated varying levels of agreement with statements related to poverty, social inequality, compassion, empathy, resilience, moral redemption, personal agency, and social responsibility. Post-exposure results showed a notable increase in agreement with statements related to empathy, compassion, and social responsibility, suggesting that experiencing the narrative of "Oliver Twist" had a positive impact on participants' attitudes.

Likert scale responses and qualitative insights were analyzed to identify changes in attitudes and beliefs regarding poverty and social inequality. Patterns in responses indicated the effectiveness of narrative storytelling in fostering empathy and raising awareness of societal issues. Participants expressed empathy and compassion towards the characters in the novel, particularly Oliver, highlighting the emotional resonance of the story. Discussions also revealed nuanced interpretations of themes such as resilience and moral redemption, with participants reflecting on the complexities of personal agency and social responsibility depicted in the narrative.

Impact on Attitudes Towards Compassion and Empathy

Experiencing the story of "Oliver Twist" fostered compassion and empathy among grade 12 STEM A students as they witnessed Oliver's struggles and the kindness of certain characters amidst a backdrop of poverty and adversity.

Pre-exposure surveys revealed baseline attitudes toward compassion and empathy. Post-exposure surveys and focus group discussions demonstrated an increase in expressions of compassion and empathy, with students citing specific scenes or characters that resonated with them.

Likert scale responses and qualitative were analyzed to assess changes in attitudes towards compassion and empathy. Themes of kindness and empathy in "Oliver Twist" influenced students' perceptions and behaviors toward others in real-life situations.

Participants exhibited empathetic responses to scenes depicting poverty and injustice, demonstrating their immersion in the narrative. Non-verbal cues, such as facial expressions and body language, further underscored participants' emotional reactions and connection to the story. Content Analysis: Content analysis of survey responses, focus group transcripts, and observational notes identified recurring themes and patterns in participants' interpretations and responses. Themes related to empathy, compassion, resilience, and social responsibility emerged prominently, reflecting the transformative impact of experiencing the narrative of "Oliver Twist" on participants' perspectives.

The results of the experiment demonstrate the profound influence of experiencing the story of "Oliver Twist" on participants' perceptions and attitudes towards themes of poverty, social inequality, compassion, empathy, resilience, moral redemption, personal agency, and social responsibility. The significant shifts observed in participants' attitudes, as evidenced by increased agreement with statements related to empathy, compassion, and social responsibility, suggest that exposure to the narrative had a positive impact on their worldview. The qualitative insights obtained from focus group discussions further elucidate the emotional resonance of the story and the nuanced interpretations of its themes among participants. Participants' expressions of empathy and compassion towards the characters in the novel highlight the power of storytelling to evoke emotional responses and foster understanding of social issues. Observations during participants' exposure to different mediums of "Oliver Twist" provided additional context to their reactions and engagement with the narrative. The observed levels of immersion and emotional involvement underscore the effectiveness of various mediums in eliciting empathetic responses and facilitating meaningful engagement with the story.

Variation in Responses Across Different Mediums

Different mediums of experiencing the story, such as audio recordings and film adaptations, elicited varying emotional responses and interpretations from students due to differences in storytelling techniques and visual cues.

Comparative analyses of survey responses and focus group discussions across different mediums revealed differences in students' emotional engagement, comprehension, and retention of key themes. Some students had connected more deeply with the written narrative, while others were moved by visual representations in film adaptations.

Data from Likert scale responses and qualitative observations were analyzed to identify trends and preferences in students' responses to different mediums. Insights gained from these comparisons can inform educators and curriculum developers in selecting effective teaching materials and resources.

Influence of Prior Knowledge and Experiences

Students' prior knowledge and experiences shaped their interpretation of the themes and messages portrayed in "Oliver Twist." Those with exposure to social issues or historical contexts similar to those depicted in the novel developed unique perspectives to their analysis.

Pre-exposure surveys captured students' backgrounds, including their familiarity with Victorian literature, historical contexts, and personal experiences related to poverty or social inequality. Post-exposure surveys and focus group discussions revealed diverse interpretations and insights influenced by students' prior knowledge and experiences.

Qualitative data were analyzed to explore the intersection of students' backgrounds with their responses to the novel. Patterns in responses reflected the interplay between personal experiences and textual interpretations, providing

a rich understanding of how individual backgrounds shape literary analysis and empathy development.

DISCUSSION

The results of the experiment demonstrate the profound influence of experiencing the story of "Oliver Twist" on participants' perceptions and attitudes towards themes of poverty, social inequality, compassion, empathy, resilience, moral redemption, personal agency, and social responsibility. The significant shifts observed in participants' attitudes, as evidenced by increased agreement with statements related to empathy, compassion, and social responsibility, suggest that exposure to the narrative had a positive impact on their worldview.

The qualitative insights gleaned from the in-depth discussions conducted in focus groups offer a deeper understanding of the profound emotional impact of "Oliver Twist" on participants. Through these discussions, participants articulated their emotional resonance with the characters and events depicted in the novel, shedding light on the nuanced interpretations they derived from the story's themes. Their expressions of empathy and compassion towards the characters underscore the transformative power of storytelling in eliciting emotional responses and fostering empathy towards societal issues portrayed in the narrative.

Furthermore, the observations made during participants' exposure to different mediums of "Oliver Twist" provide valuable context to their reactions and engagement with the story. These observations revealed the varying levels of immersion and emotional involvement exhibited by participants across different mediums, highlighting the effectiveness of each medium in evoking empathetic responses and facilitating meaningful engagement with the narrative. The observed immersion underscores the capacity of storytelling, whether through reading, watching film adaptations, or listening to audio recordings, to transport individuals into the world of the story and evoke emotional connections that transcend the boundaries of medium.

The findings of the experiment highlight the enduring significance of "Oliver Twist" in shaping perceptions and attitudes towards social issues. Through its portrayal of poverty, injustice, and resilience, the narrative serves as a poignant reminder of the struggles faced by marginalized individuals in society. Moreover, by immersing participants in the world of 19th-century London, the story prompts critical reflection on contemporary social issues and the ongoing relevance of Dickens' themes.

The narrative of "Oliver Twist" provides a platform for profound reflection and discussion among participants. By delving into themes of poverty, social inequality, and moral redemption, the story encourages individuals to confront the realities of societal challenges and consider their roles in effecting positive change. Through empathetic engagement with the characters and their struggles, participants are compelled to examine their own beliefs and values, fostering a deeper understanding of human compassion and resilience.

Furthermore, "Oliver Twist" serves as a catalyst for promoting empathy and compassion towards others. By depicting the harsh realities faced by its characters, the narrative evokes emotional responses and encourages participants to empathize with those experiencing adversity. This heightened sense of empathy can have far-reaching implications, inspiring individuals to take action and advocate for social justice in their communities.

In essence, the enduring impact of "Oliver Twist" lies in its ability to provoke thought, inspire empathy, and spark meaningful conversations about social issues. By engaging with the narrative, participants are not only transported to Victorian London but also prompted to consider their roles as active agents of change in today's society. Through continued exploration and discussion of Dickens' timeless themes, "Oliver Twist" continues to serve as a powerful tool for promoting empathy, understanding, and social consciousness among readers of all ages.

CONCLUSION

The study of "Oliver Twist" has demonstrated its profound impact on students' perceptions, attitudes, and empathetic responses towards poverty, social inequality, compassion, empathy, resilience, moral redemption, personal agency, and social responsibility. Through exposure to the narrative, students have shown increased awareness, empathy, and a sense of social responsibility, highlighting the power of literature in fostering critical thinking and ethical reflection. Furthermore, variations in responses across different mediums and the influence of prior knowledge underscore the importance of diverse pedagogical approaches and personalized learning experiences in engaging students with complex themes and messages. Ultimately, the findings of this study emphasize the enduring relevance of "Oliver Twist" and its potential to inspire empathy, resilience, and ethical citizenship in contemporary education.

Overall, the findings of the experiment underscore the enduring relevance and impact of "Oliver Twist" in shaping perceptions and attitudes towards social issues. By providing a platform for reflection and discussion, the narrative prompts participants to consider their roles in addressing societal challenges and fostering empathy and compassion towards others. The results of the experiment emphasize the lasting significance and influence of "Oliver Twist" in molding perceptions and outlooks on social issues. Through its evocative storytelling, the narrative serves as a catalyst for introspection and dialogue, encouraging participants to contemplate their responsibilities in tackling societal hurdles and cultivating empathy and understanding for others.

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